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GREEN TECHNOLOGY IN SOLID WASTE: ECOFRIENDLY REACTIONS OF BIOMASS WITH ADDITIVES

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ABSTRACT

The focus of research work is to minimize the solid waste and increase the resources of energy generation. It means solid waste management is very necessary for human beings at the modern time. We are done this process in our collage and we are used the garden waste of our collage parks. In our university, we have a large area for gardening purpose. Which a huge amount of gardening waste is generated. Typically, the garden refuse stream consists of a wide range of putrescible material including leaves, grass-clippings, perennial and annual plant material, tree and shrub branches and other woody waste, etc. We can use this waste for the production of bio gas. . There was a digester tank of 20 liter for decomposition of mixture of cow dung slurry and garden waste. Sugarcane thresh was also added for increase the production of bio gas like as additives. The garden waste was grinding by the grinder machine properly. Then, this mixture is putting for the 30 days. And then, we are seeing that tube is fully filled by the gas. The result is observed that production of biogas is mainly depended on the parameters like- pH value, temperature etc. if the pH value is approximately 7 or 7.5 , then the productivity of bio gas is also increased. So, we can maintain the pH value by the use of additives and also increase the bio gas production. And, we shall use the high temperature for this process. Because, the high temperature is increased the rate of decomposition of mixture of slurry. We are measured this parameters at the time of influent and effluent of slurry like as – temperature, pH value, total solids , volatile solids and non-volatile solids etc. The pH value of influent is 7.5 and of effluent is 5.85. And the temperature of influent is 29°C and of effluent is 32°C . These values are measured throughout the time of experimentation. This type of biogas comprises primarily methane and carbon dioxide. Bio gas production requires anaerobic digestion. My research work was to create biogas which will be more cost effective, eco-friendly, cut down on landfill waste, generate a high-quality renewable fuel, and reduce carbon dioxide & methane emissions. It is a technology for green environment and zero wastage and produces the huge amount of energy sources.

Keywords: - Anaerobic digestion, Decomposition, Gardening waste, Slurry, Solid waste.

INTRODUCTION

In modern times, Waste generation is a main problem of human life, which is increasing along with population growth, urbanization and industrialization. The quantity of waste generation is mostly associated with the economic status of the society, and the proper waste management is necessary for an improved quality of life. Continued open dumping and improper land filling of solid waste in major cities of developing world will dangerous for health and environmental conditions. It has reduced environmental impact, especially with respect to the green house gases. To minimise the problem of the environment and human health impact, the solutions are sought for the treatment of solid waste in cities and rural areas. This is possible by the use of process of anaerobic digestion.[1]

Biogas is produced from organic wastes by the action of anaerobic bacteria group decomposition. Anaerobic digestion process produces a large volume biogas yield of a mixture of animal dung and vegetable/crop waste rather than animal manure alone, and biogas production is the most suitable bioenergy technology .[2] Biogas can be produced from all kind of biological waste types, within these from the primary agricultural sectors and from various organic waste from the all society.

The largest resource of waste is represented by animal manure and slurries from cattle production units. In India, million tones of animal manure are produced every year and every day. Untreated or poorly managed animal manure become creates a major sources of air and water pollution. So, it is necessary to create a complex biogas production and utilization of wastes or refuse for energy on the environment. [3] The system must be integrated waste-management and environmental energy utilization. The subject of this research is: how to meet collectively the energy and waste disposal requirements. Biogas produced by the breakdown of organic matter through Anaerobic Digestion (AD). It is one of the renewable energy sources, like solar and wind energy. There are many characteristics that makes different from another sources of renewal energy such as this is 20% lighter than air, ignition temperature is in range of 650 to 750°C, odorless & color less gas with blue flame, having 20 mega joules (MJ) / m³ caloric value, 60% efficient to burn in conventional biogas stove [8]. The Co-digestion process has been used. Because, Co-digestion improves the methane (CH₄) quantity. Co-digestion process is supplied the missing nutrients by the use of co-substrates. It is also helpful for fulfilling the required moisture contents of the digester tank and we are using the sugarcane threshes for co-substrate [1].

The research work was done at the Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Department of Civil Engineering. In our research work, we supposed that there is an energy-producing and energy-utilizing technology which can be suitable for the all circumstances and initial conditions. And this biogas will be utilized in the mess of college hostels, electricity production and fuel purposes etc.

Composition of bio gas :- (concentration by volume) [7].

Methane	Carbon dioxide	Water	Hydrogen sulphide	Ammonia	Nitrogen	Oxygen	Hydrogen
55-60%	35-40%	2-7%	2%	0-0.05%	0-2%	0-2%	0-1%

Affecting factors:-

Many factors are affecting the decomposition process of slurry material and production of bio gas within the digester such as temperature, pH, and volatile solid concentrations and total solid concentrations during the time period of decomposition [1]. **MATERIALS AND METHOD**

Materials Used

The following materials are used in anaerobic decomposition process-

1. Cow Dung
2. Garden Waste
3. Sugarcane threshes
4. Water

Sampling

We take the garden waste (GW) from the famous garden such as- Jawahar circle, Kulish Smriti Van also known as Biodiversity Park spread in natural conditions with number of ornamental, timber, Medicinal Plants, Shrubs and Creepers and Herbs... We also take the cow dung from the dairy which is near by the collage and take the water sample from the many places .these samples of water will take for the mixing of materials which is used in bio gas production. For additives we collect the sugarcane threshes from the juice centers and mix it with the mixture .because sugarcane thresh give the huge amount of CH_4 gas content.

Experimental Design

For design of anaerobic digester, we are using the following equipments. These are as

1. Digester tank
2. Gas pipe
3. T-valve
4. Gas valve
5. Funnel
6. Butyle rubber tube

Figure 1: the setup of equipments

Experiment process

The volume of the digester is 20 liters. We shall use solid waste of 9kg which comprises of 5kg cow dung and 4kg garden waste. The digester tank will be filled with water of 10liters. We shall also used the sugarcane thresh of 0.5kg for the co-digestion process in to the mixture. The remaining space will be utilized for production of bio gas.

RESULT AND DISSCUSSION

The process of decomposition of organic compound is produced the huge amount of bio gas. After the 30 days, we are seeing that the Butyle tube is filled by gas completely. We are also seeing that the temperature of the digester tank is increased and pH value of slurry is decreased during this period. It means, that production of biogas is mainly depended on the two factors temperature and pH value both. This research work is also shown the maintenance of the value of pH. So, we can easily maintain the pH value by the use of additives like sugarcane threshes. And sugarcane threshes also gives the huge amount of methane (CH_4) content and it is simple carbohydrates. So, it is easily decomposed in the anaerobic digester. In overall study we saw that the pH of slurry must be maintained 7 or 7.5 approximately and the material should be grinder in small pieces for increase the surface area. So, the rate of decomposition process will increase in the short time. The focus of this work is to use the wastage of garden for the purpose of increase the energy sources. And maintain the eco-friendly environment by the management of garden refuse.

The following parameters are analyzed during this process at the time of influent and effluent of the slurry: - the values are as

The various parameters of inlet and outlet slurry was as follow

Parameter	pH	Temperature	Total solid	Volatile solid	Non Volatile solid	Colour of mixture
Influent	7.5	29°C	65.8%	87.04%	12.96%	Light brown
Effluent	5.85	32°C	48.18%	88.58%	11.42%	Dark brown

This **figure (3)** shows that if the volume of biogas is increased. Then, the value of pH is highly decreased. It means the pH value is indirectly proportional to the volume of biogas. So, we can easily show the relation between the pH value and volume of gas by this diagram.

This **figure (4)** shows that if the volume of gas is increased. Then, the value of temperature is increased. It means the temperature is directly proportional to the volume of gas. We can easily see the relationship between temperature and volume of gas.

If, we are plot the combined diagram (**figure 5**) of pH value and temperature with the volume of biogas. Then, the diagram will show that the volume of bio gas increased. And, the pH value is decreased and the temperature is highly raised.

Figure 3: Correlation with plot between pH value and volume of biogas (m³).

Figure 4: It shows the diagram between the temperature (°C) and volume of biogas (m³)

Figure 5: Correlation between pH, Temperature and Volume in Anaerobic Digester

We are also measuring the different- different parameters during the gap of 5 days into the period of 30 days. And it is seeing by the use of table like as:

Experimental details/Observation: -

S.No.	Time	Sample appearance	Evolution of gas	Ignition of Gas	Smell	Volume of Gas (m ³)
1	Day1	Biogas is produced and observed Half gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester rise		Smell is like CNG	0.098
2	Day5	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.452
3	Day10	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.526
4	Day15	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.591
5	Day20	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.657
6	Day25	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.752
7	Day30	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.803*

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The purpose of this project that it is full fill the requirement of biogas generation and increasing the needs of solid waste management as well as production of energy . It can be cheap as well as inexhaustible. We are take the initially samples from the possible sources with safety precaution and preparation of slurries is done by mixing the garden waste with cow dung with defined proportion of water. Then, we are analysis physic-chemical parameters of the inlet and outlet slurries from the samples. We are seeing that calculated data of the parameter of slurries reveals the high value of organic content which is easily decomposed by anaerobic bacteria and produced methane gas. Conversion of organic compound was done from higher molecular weight to lower molecular weight by the same bacteria. Generated Biogas during the digestion period was analyzed in terms of amount of biogas production as well as CH₄ and CO₂. When the temperature is increased up to 32 °C, the production of Biogas were also increased and the pH reached to the 5.85, thus we can easily say that Biogas production is depended on the temperature and pH value both parameters. For maintain the pH we can use additives like sugarcane thresh and also increase the quantity of bio gas. There is still more work to be done in near future, if the temperature and pH parameters can be control it can enhance the production of the

Biogas with same quantity of the feed materials and further measurements can be carried out with different quantity of the feed slurries to check the amount and quality of the Biogas production at the time of digestion period. This work need to be applied at larger scale so that it will bring financial benefits and ecofriendly environment, and it is proved that it is produced a good quality of effluent which can be used as a fertilizer in village areas. it will be more effective and beneficial for the crop as well as to the farmers as portable fuel. This kind of project may help us to build a safe and clean environment where fuel source can eco-friendly. And also increase the energy resources for the human beings.

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